

Participatory mapping with communities and students of Ovalau island, Fiji, in 2025

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February 2026

This report is part of the project

SOCPacific2R - A Sea of Connections: Valuing Reef Passages in the South Pacific Region.

SOCPacific2R (2024 – 2027) is conducted in cooperation between the Research Institute for Development (IRD), the Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research (ZMT) and the University of the South Pacific (USP). SOCPacific2R is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and the Agence National de la Recherche (ANR).

Funding numbers: ANR-23-FRAL-0002-01 and DFG 529664738.

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Funded by

DFG Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft
German Research Foundation

2021-2030 United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Dcennie des Nations Unies
pour les sciences ocaniques
au service du dveloppement durable

1. Introduction to the project and research context

Reef passages are natural breaks in reefs that connect the coastal zones to the open ocean. As hotspots for biodiversity reproductivity, and as pathways for fisher(wo)men as well as a variety of non-human species, they hold remarkable value for environment and society.

The project SOCPacific2R designs its research activities using an empirical inter- and transdisciplinary approach, combining natural and social sciences methods, and focuses on reef passages in Fiji and New Caledonia. The project aims to:

1. Conducting a transdisciplinary study of reef passages as under-researched features of social-ecological coral reef systems that constitute complex, interconnected, and dynamic assemblages of living and non-living, dwelling and transiting, entities that interact with each other;
2. Documenting both area-based and other management and conservation arrangements applied to reef passages, including the pros and cons that local stakeholder groups identify;
3. Establishing a participatory science-society-policy dialogue informed by social-ecological studies, Oceanian socio-cosmologies and sovereignties, and governance norms in/for the management and conservation of reef passages.

SOCPacific2R works with various stakeholders to achieve the project's goals: scientists, administrators, NGOs, and local communities. The outcomes of the project will feed into wider frameworks on marine sustainability such as the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030).

Local communities are the main knowledge holders and users of the reef passages that surround the Fijian and New Caledonian islands. The presented study aimed to learn their perspectives and experiences concerning the reef passages on Ovalau island in Fiji through an interdisciplinary research team, and was conducted by a student group of the University of the South Pacific (USP) between September 2025 and February 2026.

2. Research Methodology

The main objective of this project was to conduct a transdisciplinary study on reef passages, involving various stakeholders and valuing their knowledge, in particular that of coastal communities. To involve communities, participatory mapping was used as a collaborative tool to collect spatial data, and to represent place-based information. Participatory mapping aims to create maps with and by local people, valuing their knowledge of, experiences of, and attachment to their territory, including important places, land uses, resources, and cultural elements. It is a way to give a voice to, and empower, local communities.

Within SOCPacific2R, participatory mapping was conducted on Ovalau island, Fiji, between September and November 2025. The mapping sessions were held with adults in Vatukalo Village and Tokou Village, and with high school students at the Levuka Public School (LPS). In each location, participants were separated into two groups based on gender and engaged

in parallel mapping discussions, leading to a total of six participating groups and six resulting participatory maps. The accompanying research team also split by gender: female researchers worked with women, while male researchers worked with men. In the traditional social setting in which the sessions were held, this separation by gender ensured the inclusion of both male and female knowledge, and allowed for the visibility of gender-based perspectives on reef passages. For each participatory mapping session, the same protocol was followed to ensure that resulting maps could be compared across gender and locations.

2.1 Preparation of the maps

For these participatory mapping sessions, a total of six maps were used, one map per group. These maps covered the eastern part of Ovalau island and the southern part of the neighboring island, Moturiki. This spatial extent was selected for two main reasons: reef passages are primarily located on the eastern side of Ovalau island, which also corresponds to the study sites (Vatukalo, Levuka, Tokou – from north to south) where participatory mapping was carried out.

Figure 1: Map used for participatory mapping on Ovalau, Fiji. (a) Extent of the map, (b) Example of one of the tiles composing the map, tile number 12 in this case showing Natubari reef passage in front of Levuka town.

These maps were created in QGIS, using a Bing satellite background from the QuickMapsServices plugin. In order to cover all the reefs on this side of Ovalau island while ensuring map legibility (i.e., an appropriate scale), each map was divided into 28 separate tiles. To this end, a grid covering the entire study area was created, consisting of 28 equally sized polygons, each representing a tile at a scale of 1:5,000. The 28 tiles were then printed in A4 format and assembled using transparent adhesive tape (Figure 1), resulting in a map approximately 235 cm high and 155 cm wide. Apart from the grid, the scale bar, the North arrow and the points indicating certain reef passages, no additional elements were added to the map so as not to influence the participants.

2.2 Preparation of the participatory mapping sessions

Before starting each participatory mapping session, participants were divided into two groups based on gender (Table 1). The participants were selected using two different approaches. In both villages, the activity was announced during the *sevusevu*: a traditional Fijian ceremony in which visitors formally present kava to the village chief, in this case to inform them about the project and seek endorsement to conduct research in the village. The village headman relayed the information and set the date. Those who were willing and available chose to take part. At Levuka Public School, the student participation was coordinated through the Principal and Assistant Principal. Once all participants had arrived, the researchers sought FPIC (Free, Prior and Informed Consent) before the start of the session through an oral agreement.

Each session followed a standardized protocol (Attachment01), which details the methodological steps, the corresponding guiding questions, and the cartographic symbology and material to be used, resulting in each session lasting approximately one hour to one and a half hours. Stickers, sticky notes and chalk markers of different colors and/or shapes were used in accordance with a shared legend or key (Figure 2), in order to differentiate various types of places and organize spatial information.

During the participatory mapping sessions, members of the research team rotated roles, including facilitation, note-taking, participant observation, photographic documentation, and the distribution of material. This collaborative rotation supported multiple forms of documentation and ensured attentiveness to both interactions between participants and the fluidity of the mapping process, while also allowing team members - particularly interns - to get involved, learn, and gain confidence in a range of tasks.

Table 1. Summary information on participatory mapping sessions and participants.

Location	Date	Participants	
Tokou Village	29/09/2025	18 women, age 24 – 93	17 men, age 20 – 50
Vatukalo Village	25/09/2025	6 women, age 30 – 57	9 men, age 14 – 50+
Levuka Public School, Levuka Town	06/10/2025	12 girls, age 14 – 17	12 boys, age 14 – 16

2.3 Mental maps as an ice-breaker and drawing exercise tool

As an opening activity for each session, the facilitator of each group (men or women) asked the participants to draw, on an A4 paper using pencils and colored pencils, a mental map of their *vanua*: a Fijian concept that connects the land and the sea, resources, human communities (with their socio-political organization), and the cultural and spiritual dimensions that link them. This initial activity was conducted as an individual and personal exercise, in contrast to the collective and participatory mapping carried out afterward. The drawings

were subsequently compared and discussed in exchanges between the researchers and participants, and among participants themselves.

This step functioned primarily as a facilitative tool and ice-breaker, fostering a climate of trust and encouraging expression and dialogue. Although the drawings were subsequently collected and photographed, they were not incorporated into this study nor subjected to formal interpretive analysis.

2.4 Participatory mapping

Following the mental mapping activity, the prepared map (see 2.1) was brought in and laid out on the ground. The participants then gathered around it to familiarize themselves with the map - for example, by locating their village or other landmarks - and discussed among themselves for a few minutes. This was followed by discussions between the participants and the researchers (facilitator and note-takers), with the steps and guiding questions organized into several topics: (i) fishing activity, (ii) reef passages, and (iii) governance, management, and conservation (Attachment01).

Participants were invited to identify areas that they personally value, or that are culturally or ecologically important, as well as other significant marine sites, such as fishing grounds, reef passages, *tabu* areas (i.e., areas where fishing and sometimes other activities are restricted for customary reasons and/or management purposes), or areas to preserve for future generations. In order to enable comparisons between maps and to analyze them according to gender and locations, participants were required to use a specific set of symbols for each element of the legend (Figure 2). For instance, they were asked to identify and circle their fishing grounds using a yellow chalk pen and to attach sticky notes specifying the fishing practices associated with each ground.

Figure 2: Shared legend for the preliminary six maps.

In addition to obtaining consent for participation, participants were also asked to provide separate consent regarding the sharing of the maps that resulted from the session/activity, both inside and outside the community.

Overall, this participatory mapping activity provided the participants with a visual support to facilitate the clear articulation and representation of their spatial uses and knowledge of their local coastal environment, in particular reef passages, and to explore spatial differences in practices and knowledge between men/boys and women/girls. Moreover, because the participatory mapping sessions involved multiple generations with a wide age range, this

diversity of participants brought together different and complementary viewpoints, enriching the discussion on reef passages while allowing both peer and intergenerational learning.

2.5 Digitization of the maps

The maps produced during the participatory mapping sessions were systematically photographed to enable georeferencing, allowing for precise spatial positioning of the recorded information. Subsequently, all features and annotations depicted on the maps were digitized, creating a comprehensive digital dataset that could be integrated into a GIS (geographic information system).

2.6 Validation and correction of the maps in exchange with participants

The resulting digital maps were printed using a grid of six A4-size tiles at a scale of 1:30,000 taped together, resulting in a map approximately 95 cm high and 45 cm wide (Figure 3).

These maps were presented to participants at Levuka Public School and in Tokou Village in November 2025, but not in Vatukalo Village due to time constraints. Men/boys and women/girls (in separate groups) were invited to review, correct, and supplement the maps, validate them, and subsequently engage in a joint discussion of gender-based differences (Figure 4). Like before, the research team requested confirmation of permission to share the resulting adjusted maps both within and beyond the community.

2.7. Harmonization of contents and finalization of the maps

The corrected maps were photographed, georeferenced, and digitized using the same methods as for the preliminary results (see 2.5). Additional processing was subsequently carried out to standardize map symbology and ensure consistency and clarity in the layout and legend, resulting in six final comparable maps (Attachment02). In particular, additional processing was required for the category "other human activities" carried out in or near reef passages that participants identified and represented/localized by different colored points.

This open-ended question allowed participants to indicate various types of activities, which resulted in substantial variability across maps. A classification decision was therefore necessary to group these activities into coherent categories, based on their nature (e.g., pollution and degradation, picnic spots, boat traffic, etc.). For example, human activities labeled by the participants as "Burning of trees", "Deforestation", "Dynamite fishing", "Factory waste", "Oil spill", "Pollution", "Shipwreck", and "Water pollution" were grouped under "Pollution and degradation".

Figure 3: Preliminary digitalized results from the participatory mapping session with the girls of Levuka Public School.

Figure 4: Photo of the girls' map after the feedback of the girls and the boys of Levuka Public School in November 2025.

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